

ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES IN AN EFFORTS TO INCREASE COMMUNITY INCOME IN THE MARINA TOGO MOWONDU TOURISM AREA, WANGI-WANGI DISTRICT, WAKATOBI REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze business opportunities in an effort to enhance community income in the Marina Togo Mowondu tourism area, Wangi-Wangi District, Wakatobi Regency. This research employs a qualitative descriptive approach, using data collection techniques such as in-depth interviews, observations, and document analysis. The participants involved in this study included local business operators, tourists, and relevant stakeholders. Data analysis was conducted using the Miles and Huberman interactive model, consisting of data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. The findings indicate that the Marina Togo Mowondu tourism area possesses significant business potential in the culinary sector, souvenirs trade, transportation services, and tourism-based creative industries. The availability of natural tourism attractions, the increasing number of tourist visits, and active community participation serve as supporting factors for the development of these business opportunities. However, several constraints were identified, including infrastructure limitations, inadequate business management skills, and a lack of promotional strategies. Therefore, community capacity building, infrastructure improvement, and the optimization of digital marketing are required to foster business growth and ensure a sustainable increase in community income.

Keywords: Business Opportunities , Income , Tourism Area

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector plays a strategic role in driving regional economic growth, particularly in improving the welfare and income of local communities. As a leading marine tourism destination in Indonesia, Wakatobi Regency holds significant potential for developing tourism-based economic activities. One area with such potential is the Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area in Wangi-Wangi District. This area not only serves as a tourist attraction but also provides business opportunities for the surrounding

community in various sectors, including culinary, trade, services, and the creative industry. Based on previous research studies (state of the art), the development of tourist destinations has made a significant contribution to improving the local economy. Research by Putra (2020) shows that tourism activities can open up new business opportunities, especially for coastal communities.

Furthermore, Sari and Nugroho (2021) stated that strengthening tourism-based micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) can sustainably increase community income. Research by Rahman (2022) revealed that implementing digital marketing strategies plays a crucial role in expanding market access for local businesses. Furthermore, Lestari (2023) emphasized that active community involvement in managing tourist destinations can increase the region's competitiveness. Research by Hidayat (2024) also demonstrated that developing a tourism-based creative economy can strengthen regional economic resilience. However, there remains a gap between the potential and the level of utilization of business opportunities in tourism areas, particularly in Marina Togo Momodu. Some of the challenges faced include limited facilities and infrastructure, poor managerial skills among business owners, and suboptimal promotional strategies. This indicates that available business opportunities are not being fully utilized to increase community income.

Therefore, a more in-depth study is needed to identify business potential and formulate appropriate development strategies. Conceptually, this research draws on the theories of business opportunities, tourism development, and community economic empowerment. Business opportunity theory emphasizes an individual's ability to recognize and exploit existing economic opportunities (Drucker, 1985). Meanwhile, the concept of tourism development focuses on optimally utilizing tourism resources to improve community welfare (Yoeti, 2008). Furthermore, community empowerment theory emphasizes the importance of active community involvement in the economic development process (Chambers, 1995). Problem-solving efforts in this research were carried out through a qualitative approach by identifying various business potentials, obstacles faced, and development strategies that can be implemented.

The solutions offered include improving the quality of human resources, strengthening digital-based promotional strategies, and developing supporting infrastructure for the tourism sector. The novelty of this research lies in its focus on specifically analyzing business opportunities in the still-limited Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area, integrating business opportunity analysis with increasing local community income. Based on this description, the purpose of this study is to analyze business opportunities to increase community income in the Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area, Wangi-Wangi District, Wakatobi Regency. The hypothesis proposed in this study is that the more optimally utilized tourism-based business opportunities, the greater the increase in community income in the area.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive approach. This approach was chosen to gain a deeper understanding of business opportunities to increase community income in the Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area. Qualitative research allows researchers to directly explore phenomena based on real-world conditions through interactions with informants. This research focuses on emerging business opportunities in the Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area. The focus of the research includes analysis of business potential, obstacles faced by business actors, and development strategies to increase community income. The variables or aspects studied include tourism-based business opportunities, levels of community participation, and supporting and inhibiting factors for business development.

This research was conducted in the Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area, located in Wangi-Wangi District, Wakatobi Regency. The location was selected based on the consideration that this area is a tourist destination with economic potential for the local community. Informants in this study were business actors and residents involved in economic activities in the tourist area. Informants were determined using a purposive sampling technique, selecting informants who were considered to have knowledge and experience related to the research focus. Informants in this study consisted of business actors (culinary, trade, services), tourism area managers, and tourists. The research instrument used was the researcher herself, supported by interview guidelines, observation sheets, and documentation. The interview guidelines were used to gather in-depth information from informants, while observations were conducted to directly observe economic activities taking place at the research site. Documentation, in the form of photographs, archives, and related notes, served as supporting data. Data collection techniques were carried out through in-depth interviews, direct field observations, and documentation studies. Interviews were conducted semi-structured to provide flexibility in gathering relevant information. Observations were conducted to understand the actual conditions and social interactions occurring in the tourist area. Documentation was used to complement and strengthen the data from interviews and observations. The data analysis technique in this study uses the Miles and Huberman model which includes three stages, namely data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions.

Data reduction involves selecting and simplifying data relevant to the research focus. Data is presented in descriptive narrative form for ease of understanding. Conclusions are then drawn based on the analysis results to address the research objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on research conducted in the Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area, it was found that several types of business opportunities are developing and contributing to increasing community income. The data obtained has been processed and presented in the following table:

Mowondu Marina Tourism Area

No	Type of business	Number of Business Actors	Percentage (%)
1	Culinary	15	37.5
2	Souvenir Trading	8	20
3	Transportation Services	7	17.5
4	Tourist Equipment Rental	5	12.5
5	Other Creative Businesses	5	12.5
	Total	40	100

Data processed by researchers in 2026

Based on Table 1, the most dominant type of business is culinary, with a percentage of 37.5%, followed by souvenir trading at 20%. This indicates that basic tourist needs, such as consumption, are a primary business opportunity for the community. Furthermore, transportation services and tourist equipment rentals have also grown significantly in line with the increase in tourist visits. Interviews with informants support these findings. Mr. Ahmad explained that his culinary business has experienced significant growth, especially on weekends and during the holiday season. He stated that daily revenue can increase up to twofold compared to normal days due to the high number of tourists. Ms. Siti Rahma expressed a similar sentiment, stating that handicrafts such as bracelets and traditional regional ornaments have a unique appeal to tourists, although she acknowledged that marketing is still carried out in a simple manner and has not yet utilized digital media optimally. Furthermore, Mr. La Ode Rudi explained that demand for transportation services is increasing along with the growing number of tourists, particularly for shuttle services from ports and airports to tourist destinations. However, he stated that the limited number of vehicles is a major obstacle in meeting this demand.

Meanwhile, Mr. Arman emphasized that this area has great potential to be developed into a leading destination, but still requires better infrastructure support and broader promotion to reach tourists both nationally and internationally. Furthermore, interviews with Nurhayati revealed that rental businesses for tourist equipment, such as life jackets and snorkeling gear, are starting to grow, particularly among younger tourists. She stated that the increase in visitor numbers has had a direct impact on revenue, although equipment availability remains limited. Meanwhile, Andi Saputra stated that the Togo Mowondu Marina area offers attractive views and is a pleasant place to visit, but public facilities such as cleanliness, rest areas, and better road access are still needed.

Another finding was obtained by Ms. Wa Ode Lina, who revealed that business opportunities in the creative economy sector, such as producing traditional foods and handicrafts, are quite promising, especially if supported by government training and guidance. She believes that improving skills and product innovation are essential for businesses to be able to compete with products from other regions.

Table 2. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors of Business Opportunities

No	Supporting factors	Inhibiting Factors
1	Natural tourism potential	Infrastructure limitations
2	High number of tourist visits	Limited business capital
3	Community Participation	Low managerial skills
4	Strategic location	Lack of digital promotion

Based on Table 2, the main supporting factors for developing business opportunities are attractive natural tourism potential and increasing tourist visits. Community participation and strategic locations are also crucial factors in driving business growth. However, various obstacles remain, such as limited infrastructure, lack of business capital, poor managerial skills, and suboptimal use of digital promotions. Overall, the research results indicate that business opportunities in the Marina Togo Mowondu tourist area offer excellent prospects for increasing community income. This is supported by interviews, which indicated an increase in community economic activity. However, more targeted efforts are needed to address various obstacles so that this potential can be utilized optimally and sustainably.

1. Dynamics and Distribution Patterns of Business Opportunities in Tourist Areas

Based on the research results presented in Table 1, it is clear that there has been an economic transformation in the Togo Mowondu Marina Tourism area. Of the 40 identified business actors, the distribution of business types shows a pyramid pattern typical of developing tourism destinations. Culinary businesses dominate with the highest percentage at 37.5% (15 businesses), followed by souvenir trading at 20% (8 businesses). The dominance of the culinary sector can be explained using Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. In the context of tourism, physiological needs (food and drink) are basic needs. *need*) that is most sought after and definitely consumed by tourists, regardless of their market segment. In addition, according to the concept of Consumer Behavior of Tourists (Consumer According to Swarbrooke and Horner's (2007) "Behavior in Tourism," tourists tend to be heterogeneous in terms of attractions but homogeneous in terms of basic needs. This makes the culinary sector a business with the lowest risk but the fastest turnover. In second and third place, souvenir trading (20%) and transportation services (17.5%) indicate that this region is entering a phase of economic diversification. The presence of five tourism equipment rental businesses (12.5%) and five other creative businesses (12.5%) indicates the emergence of demand

for special recreational activities. Interest According to Butler 's (1980) *Tourism Area Life Cycle* (TALC) theory, this condition illustrates that the Togo Mowondu Marina area is in transition from the *Involvement stage* (spontaneous community involvement) to the *Development stage*, where local communities begin to recognize and capitalize on the flow of tourists in a structured manner.

2. Contribution of Business Opportunities to Increasing Community Income

The emerging business opportunities are not only quantitative (number of players) but also have a qualitative impact on community income. This is evidenced by the statement of Mr. Ahmad (a culinary entrepreneur) who experienced a doubling of daily income on weekends and during the holiday season. This phenomenon is known in tourism economics literature as seasonality. Multiplier Seasonal Multiplier Effect, where a surge in demand at a certain time creates a cash *injection* significant *injection into the household economy*. Ms. Nurhayati felt a similar impact in the tourism equipment rental sector (life jackets and snorkeling). Demand from this young tourist segment indicates that the Marina Togo Mowondu area is a potential destination. successfully attracting millennials and Gen Z, who tend to have *experiential* consumption patterns (seeking experiences). The increase in income experienced by Ms. Nurhayati directly validates the Economic Base Theory, which states that the export sector (in this case, tourists from outside the region who come and spend their money) is a basic sector that brings new income to the region, which then drives the growth of the local household sector. Furthermore, Mr. La Ode Rudi's transportation service has also seen an increase in demand for shuttle services (from airports/ports to tourist locations). This demonstrates that business opportunities do not stand alone but rather form a value chain). Improvements in the marina attraction sector have triggered a series of positive effects on the transportation, accommodation, and culinary sectors.

3. Analysis of Supporting and Inhibiting Factors for Business Development

Although business opportunities show bright prospects, their development cannot be separated from the dynamics of supporting and inhibiting factors as summarized in Table 2. Supporting Factors: Natural tourism potential and strategic location are the main attractions (*pull factor*) for tourists. According to the 4A model of Tourism Destinations (Cooper et al., 1993), Marina Togo Mowondu has *Attractions* (attractions in the form of sea views) and *Accessibility* (easy accessibility from the city center/port). The high number of tourist visits and active community participation (40 business actors) indicate the existence of good Social Capital. The community does not only play a role as spectators, but has become *a subject* in tourism development.

Inhibiting Factors: However, the identified inhibiting factors indicate an imbalance between demand growth and supply capacity. Mr. La Ode Rudi's statement regarding the limited number of vehicles and Ms. Nurhayati's statement regarding the limited rental equipment are theoretically referred to as Capacity Deficit (Capacity Deficit). When demand exceeds supply, *an opportunity arises. cost* (opportunity cost) in

the form of income that could have been obtained by the community but was lost due to the inability to provide services. Andi Saputra and Arman also issued harsh criticism regarding infrastructure and public facilities. According to the UNWTO's Sustainable Tourism concept, destination quality is measured not only by natural beauty but also by basic service standards such as cleanliness (sanitation), rest areas, and road access. These infrastructure limitations have the potential to degrade *a destination. image* (destination image) and trigger tourist dissatisfaction.

4. Managerial Challenges, Product Innovation, and Marketing Digitalization

The research findings revealed a critical fact: despite the wide-open business opportunities, the quality of business management remains traditional. This is reflected in Ms. Siti Rahma's statement, which acknowledged that souvenir marketing is still carried out in a simplistic manner and has not yet optimally utilized digital media.

This condition can be analyzed using the Innovation Adoption Theory (Innovation Adoption Theory). Diffusion Theory) from Everett Rogers. MSMEs in Marina Togo Mowondu are still considered *laggards*, or late in adopting technological innovations (digital marketing). In the *Industry 4.0 era*, the inability to utilize digital platforms (such as social media, *marketplaces*, or Google My Business) creates *information Asymmetry* (information gap). Tourists are unaware of Ibu Siti Rahma's flagship products, thus hindering the potential for increased revenue. On the other hand, Ms. Wa Ode Lina highlighted the importance of product innovation for competitiveness. This statement aligns with the Competitive Advantage Theory Advantage) from Michael Porter (1990), which emphasizes that in market competition, product differentiation is the main key.

If the handicrafts and traditional foods sold are only generic (the same as those sold in other regions), their bargaining power and selling value will be low. Attractive packaging and a strong local touch (such as incorporating Wakatobi cultural stories into the product) are needed to create *value. added* (added value). Furthermore, low managerial skills (Table 2) indicate that business owners generally lack a grasp of basic financial *literacy concepts, such as calculating* the break -even point (BEP), recording cash flow, and strategic pricing. Without these skills, increased turnover (as experienced by Mr. Ahmad) does not guarantee a commensurate increase in net profit.

5. Synthesis and Policy Implications

Overall, the Togo Mowondu Marina Tourism area has a proven ecosystem of business opportunities that is already operating and proven to increase community income. However, current growth is more *organic* (growing naturally following the flow of tourists) and not yet structured (planned and managed systematically). Referring to the principles of Community-Based Tourism (CBT) (Scheyvens, 1999), to optimally and sustainably utilize this business potential, the following policy synergy is needed:

1. **Strengthening Human Resources Capacity (Capacity) Building):** The Wangi-Wangi District Government together with related agencies must hold basic business management training and digital marketing literacy

(photography/video content, use of social media) for business actors such as Mrs. Siti Rahma and Mrs. Wa Ode Lina.

2. *Common Facilities Facilities*): Overcoming the limited capital for equipment (complaints from Mrs. Nurhayati) and vehicles (complaints from Mr. La Ode Rudi) can be done by forming a tourism cooperative that rents out equipment on a *shared basis. economy*, so that the burden of capital is not borne by individuals.
3. *Basic Infrastructure Intervention*: Mr. Arman and Mr. Andi Saputra's demands must be a priority in the Musrenbang. Road repairs, the addition of clean public toilets, and adequate *parking areas are absolute requirements (enabling environment)* so that culinary and souvenir business opportunities can operate comfortably.

By shifting the development approach from simply “selling merchandise” to “providing an integrated tourism experience”, business opportunities in Marina Togo Mowondu will not only increase community income quantitatively, but also create a resilient local economy against tourism fluctuations.

CONCLUSION

Mowondu Marina Tourism area, Wangi-Wangi District, Wakatobi Regency, the following conclusions can be drawn:

First, there are five main business opportunity clusters that are growing and directly contributing to increasing community income, namely: (1) Culinary businesses (37.5%), (2) Souvenir trade (20%), (3) Transportation services (17.5%), (4) Tourism equipment rental (12.5%), and (5) Other creative businesses (12.5%). The dominance of the culinary and souvenir sectors shows that fulfilling basic needs (consumption) and souvenir needs are still the main economic pillars that are most easily accessible to local communities. Second, these business opportunities have been empirically proven to increase community income. This is indicated by the increase in daily turnover of business operators during the holiday season and weekends (such as in the culinary and tourist equipment rental sectors), as well as the increasing frequency of requests for tourist shuttle services. This growth demonstrates an economic multiplier effect. *positive effect of the tourism sector on the household economy in the surrounding area.*

Third, although business opportunities have excellent prospects, their development is still proceeding organically (naturally) and is not yet optimally structured. Business growth is supported by supporting factors such as the beauty of natural tourism potential, strategic location, and high community participation. However, this growth is hampered by crucial inhibiting factors, namely: (1) a deficit in business capacity due to limited capital and equipment, (2) low digital literacy and managerial skills of business actors in marketing products, and (3) the still minimal quality of infrastructure and basic supporting facilities (cleanliness, rest areas, road access) in the marina area.

Overall, the Togo Mowondu Marina Tourism area has strong tourism economic fundamentals. To transform this business opportunity into a sustainable welfare engine, policy synergy is needed from the local government and stakeholders through three strategic steps: (1) increasing the human resource capacity of MSMEs (management training and marketing digitalization), (2) facilitating capital or establishing tourism cooperatives to overcome equipment limitations, and (3) improving the area's basic infrastructure to increase comfort and extend the length of stay (length of stay) of stay tourists.

REFERENCES

- Central Statistics Agency of Wakatobi Regency. (2024). *Wakatobi Regency in figures 2024*. Wakatobi: BPS.
- Butler, R. W. (1980). The concept of a tourist area cycle of evolution : Implications for management of resources . *Canadian Geographer* , 24 (1), 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0064.1980.tb00970.x>
- Buhalis, D. (2000). Marketing the competitive destination of the future . *Tourism Management* , 21 (1), 97–116. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(99\)00095-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(99)00095-3)
- Chambers, R. (1995). *Rural development : Putting the last first* . London: Longman .
- Cooper, C., Fletcher, J., Gilbert, D., & Wanhill, S. (1993). *Tourism: Principles and practice* . Pitman Publishing .
- Wakatobi Regency Tourism Office. (2023). *Statistics of tourist visits to Wakatobi Regency in 2022/2023* . Wakatobi Regency Government.
- Drucker, P. F. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship* . New York : Harper & Row .
- Hidayat, R., Pratama, A., & Kurniawan, D. (2024). Tourism- based creative economy development and its impact on regional economic resilience . *Journal of Regional Economic Development* , 9(1), 33–48.
- Lestari, D., Wibowo, S., & Rahmawati, N. (2023). Community participation in sustainable tourism development : Evidence from local Indonesian destinations . *Journal of Tourism Studies* , 11(2), 95–110.
- Maslow, AH (1943). A theory of human motivation . *Psychological Review* , 50 (4), 370–396. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0054346>
- Pine, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1999). *The experience economy : Competing for stage time* . Harvard Business Review Press .
- Porter, M. E. (1990). *The competitive advantage of nations* . Free Press .
- Putra, IGN, & Astuti, NW (2020). The role of tourism sector in improving coastal community income . *Journal of Tourism and Economic Development* , 13(1), 1–14.
- Rahman, A., Yusuf, M., & Arifin, Z. (2022). Digital marketing strategies for SMEs in tourism sector : Enhancing competitiveness and income . *International Journal of Business and Management Studies* , 14(3), 205–219.
- Rogers, EM (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press .
- Sari, N., Nugroho, R., & Santoso, B. (2021). Strengthening tourism-based SMEs to support local economic growth . *Journal of Creative Economy* , 7(2), 80–96.

- Scheyvens , R. (1999). Ecotourism and the empowerment of local communities . *Tourism Management* , 20 (2), 245–249. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(98\)00096-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(98)00096-5)
- Swarbrooke , J. , & Horner , S. (2007). *Consumer behavior in tourism* (2nd ed.). Butterworth-Heinemann .
- United Nations World Tourism Organization [UNWTO]. (2019). *Global code of ethics for tourism* . UNWTO. <https://www.unwto.org/global-code-of-ethics-for-tourism>
- World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). (2023). *Tourism for sustainable development goals* . Madrid: UNWTO.
- Yoeti , OA (2008). *Tourism planning and development* . Jakarta: Pradnya Paramita.